

The spider genus *Oecobius* (Araneae: Oecobiidae) in Israel, with description of a new species and new synonymies

YURI M. MARUSIK ²

¹*Institute for Biological Problems of the North, 18 Portovaya Str., Magadan, 685000, Russia; Department of Zoology & Entomology, University of the Free State, Bloemfontein, 9300, South Africa; Altai State University, 61 Lenina Pr., Barnaul, RF-656049, Russia. E-mail: yurmar@mail.ru*

²*The Steinhardt Museum of Natural History, Tel Aviv University, 12 Klausner Str., Tel Aviv, 69978, Israel. E-mail: serzon56@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

An annotated list of nine species of *Oecobius* Lucas, 1846, known from Israel to date, is given. Five of them are recorded in the country for the first time; the previous tentative records of another two species in Israel are confirmed. Two names, *Hersiliola brachyplura* Strand, 1913 and *Hersiliola b. demaculata* Strand, 1914 are considered junior subjective synonyms of the widespread *O. navus* Blackwall, 1859. A new species, *O. armiachi* n. sp. is described from Israel based on both sexes. The new species differs from all congeners by the shape of the copulatory organs, and most likely represents a yet undescribed genus.

KEYWORDS: Aranei, Oecobiinae, disc web spiders, wall spiders, new records, new synonymy, Near East.

INTRODUCTION

Oecobius Lucas, 1846 is the most species-rich genus of Oecobiidae Blackwall, 1862, with 75% (96 of 127) of all extant species assigned to the family (WSC 2024). The genus is distributed in the Holarctic, Afrotropical and Oriental realms; almost half of the species are restricted to the Canary Islands (41) and the Mediterranean region (at least 15 species). The real diversity of the described species can be lower, given that 10 species described from the Canary Islands are known from females and six from males only (WSC 2024). Species occurring in the Mediterranean have been revised by Wunderlich (1995) and are considered well studied.

So far, three named species and one subspecies of *Oecobius*, have been recorded in Israel; the same number of species are known in Lebanon, one in Syria and one in Jordan (WSC 2024). Each country seems to have a unique set of species not occurring in the neighbouring countries.

Among the *Oecobius* species noted for Israel, only *O. navus* Blackwall, 1859 is a well-studied taxon, which presence in the country is confirmed and properly documented. Two other taxa, *O. brachyplura* (Strand, 1913) and *O. b. demaculatus* (Strand, 1914), both from the same region (environs of Tel Aviv), were textually described in detail, but not illustrated. Platnick (2008) indicated in his catalog that the two taxa were described based on juveniles, although Fet (2008) noted that

their types included adult specimens. Finally, *O. teliger* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872 and *O. trimaculatus* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872 have been noted for Israel as dubious records.

While studying spiders of Israel we revealed several additional congeners and found specimens of *Oecobius* that have copulatory organs different from all known species. The goal of this paper is to provide a new information, including a description of a new species.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Specimens were photographed using a Canon® EOS 7D camera (or EOS 80D camera) attached to an Olympus SZX16 stereomicroscope or to the eyepiece of an Olympus® BH2 transmission microscope at the Zoological Museum of the University of Turku, Finland, and an Olympus SZX16 stereomicroscope equipped with a Canon® EOS 80D camera at the Steinhardt Museum of Natural History, Tel Aviv, Israel (SMNHTAU). Digital images were stacked with Helicon Focus™ 8.1.1 and edited using CorelDraw® Graphics Suite X6 and Adobe® Photoshop CC. The endogyne was cleared and cleaned from soft tissues after treatment in a 10% KOH aqueous solution. Body measurements exclude the chelicerae and spinnerets. All measurements are given in mm. Lengths of leg segments were measured along the dorsal side. The types of the newly described species are stored at SMNHTAU.

TAXONOMY

Family Oecobiidae Blackwall, 1862

Genus *Oecobius* Lucas, 1846

***Oecobius armiachi* n. sp.**

(Figs 1–3)

LSID: urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:76A9FF26-D137-4966-8D9E-8C2A7E4E1D1E

Etymology: The new species is named after our colleague Igor Armiach Steinpress (formerly from the National Natural History Collections, The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, currently in the Plant Protection and Inspection Services, the Ministry of Agriculture, Bet Dagan, Israel).

Diagnosis: Male of the new species is somewhat similar to those of *O. affinis* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872 and *O. cambridgei* Wunderlich, 1995 in having a small embolic division thinner than the tegulum, but differs in having several loops (*Ls*) of the sperm duct baso-prolaterally (vs. one loop) and 5 spines on the cymbial tip (vs. 2). The structure of the epigyne in the new species is distinguishable due to the presence of a square-shaped epigynal plate with a wide slightly biconcave septum. Among the congeners with known females, a somewhat similar epigynal structures are known only for *O. nadiae* (Spassky, 1936), but in the latter species the epigynal plate is much wider and transversely ellipsoidal, and the septum is considerably narrower (Fig. 3 cf. Zarikian *et al.* 2022, fig. 7D).

Description: Male (holotype). Habitus as in Fig. 1B, C. Total length 2.33.

Color in alcohol: Carapace brown with irregular blackish pattern, pair of dark stripes separating cephalic part from thoracic, thoracic part with mesal dark stripe. Sternum brownish lacking distinct pattern, margins dark. Labium light brown, endites pale yellow. Abdomen dorsum variegated, with dark spots in mesal part, pair of subtransverse dark bands posteriorly and numerous white guanine spots; venter:

Fig. 1. *Oecobius armiachi* n. sp., holotype male (B, C) and paratype female (A, D), habitus: (A, B) dorsal, (C, D) ventral. Scale = 0.5 mm.

epigaster dark brown, postgaster with median dark band widening posteriorly, sides brownish, laterally from band with lighter area with few small white guanine spots. Spinnerets and cribellum pale yellow in ventral view, posterior lateral spinnerets dorsally brown. Legs pale yellow with dark annulation on femora, tibiae, metatarsi

Fig. 2. *Oecobius armiachi* n. sp., paratype male: (A, B) entire palp, retro- and pro-lateral; (C, D) terminal part of palp, ventral and anterior. Scale = 0.2 mm. Abbreviations: *Ce* – claw-like extension, *Ed* – embolic division, *Em* – embolus, *Ls* – loops of sperm duct, *Ra* – anterior radical apophysis, *Rp* – posterior radical apophysis, *Sd* – sperm duct, *Ta* – terminal apophysis, *Tb* – tegular beak.

and tarsi; femora, tibiae and metatarsi with two rings, tarsi with dark proximal parts; palps: trochanter, femur, patella and tibia pale yellow in lateral view, with dorsal spot on femur and tibia, cymbium and bulb orange.

Carapace: 0.84 long, 1.02 wide. *Eyes*: AME 0.05, ALE 0.04, PLE 0.07, PME (long-oval) 0.07, AME–AME 0.09, AME–ALE 0.04, ALE–PLE 0.05, PLE–PME 0.01, PME–PME 0.06.

Palp and legs: Length as indicated below:

	Palp	I	II	III	IV
Femur	0.43	0.87	0.85	0.83	0.90
Patella	0.25	0.39	0.37	0.31	0.38
Tibia	0.14	0.65	0.59	0.71	0.84
Metatarsus	–	0.62	0.71	0.69	0.87
Tarsus	0.66	0.47	0.48	0.45	0.47
Total	1.48	3.00	3.00	2.99	3.46

Palp (Fig. 2): femur ca. 2.6× as long as wide; patella longer than tibia; tibia 1.3× as wide as long; cymbium ca. 1.5× as long as wide, with short tip, tip with 5 spines; bulb ovate, ca. 1.2× as long as wide; sperm duct (*Sd*) encircling tegulum not forming any loops from retrolateral to prolateral side, but only in basal-prolateral part forming 3 loops (*Ls*); anterior part of tegulum with heavily sclerotized beak (*Tb*) above embolic division (*Ed*); embolic division not protruding, 2× as thin as tegulum in retrolateral view; terminal apophysis (*Ta*) large but not protruding, with claw-like extension (*Ce*) directed retrolaterally, radical apophysis subdivided in 2 parts, anterior with 2 processes, anterior (*Ra*) and posterior (*Rp*); embolus (*Em*) short, thorn-like.

Female (paratype). Habitus as in Fig. 1A, D. Total length 2.38.

Color in alcohol: Carapace, sternum, endites, labium and legs as in male. Abdomen dorsally lacking distinct pattern; venter with light epigaster and blacking book lungs, postgaster with mesal light band surrounded with pair of dark stripes and light submarginal bands with few large guanine spots.

Carapace: 0.81 long, 1.01 wide. *Eyes*: AME 0.06, ALE 0.05, PLE 0.08, PME (long-oval) 0.07, AME–AME 0.06, AME–ALE 0.03, ALE–PLE 0.04, PLE–PME 0.02, PME–PME 0.06.

Palp and legs: Length as indicated below:

	Palp	I	II	III	IV
Femur	0.39	0.83	0.79	0.75	1.06
Patella	0.18	0.36	0.35	0.31	0.39
Tibia	0.23	0.61	0.62	0.56	0.68
Metatarsus	–	0.58	0.46	0.63	0.72
Tarsus	0.40	0.45	0.46	0.42	0.45
Total	1.20	2.83	2.68	2.67	3.30

Fig. 3. *Oecobius armiachi* n. sp., epigyne of paratype female: (A) intact, ventral; (B) macerated, ventral. Scale = 0.2 mm. Abbreviations: Bu – bursa; Re – receptacle; Se – septum.

Epigyne (Fig. 3): Epigynal plate as long as wide, almost square-shaped, with distinct septum (*Se*), 2× as long as wide; bursae (*Bu*) large, 1.75× as long as epigynal plate, and almost as wide as plate; receptacles (*Re*) closely spaced, globular, as wide as septum.

Holotype: ♂ (SMNH_{TAU}), **Israel:** *Judean Hills:* Ben Shemen Forest Park, Mizpe Modi'in, 31°57'N 34°57'E, 160 m, 27.iv.2021, S. Zonstein.

Paratypes: 1♂, 2♀ (SMNHTAU), same collection data; collected together with the holotype.

Other material examined: Israel: *Judean Hills:* 20♂, 'Adullam Forest Nature Reserve south of Bet Shemesh, 300–350m, pitfall traps, 20.v.2002, Y. Mandelik & A. Landsman (SMNHTAU); 1♂, same but 20.v.2008, O. Skutelsky (SMNHTAU); 6♂, foothills near Yishpro, 3 km W Modi'in, 31°53'N 34°59'E, 200 m, 9–17.v.2012, I. Bernstein (SMNHTAU); 1♂, Qedoshim Forest 7 km NE Bet Shemesh, 31°47.1'N 35°03.9'E, 600 m, 30.vi.2014, G. Kapp (SMNHTAU). *Northern Negev:* 1♂, Nahal haBesor, 31°18'N 34°29'E, 70 m, 8.iv.2010, L. Friedman & C. Drees (SMNHTAU).

Distribution: Israel: Judean Hills and Northern Negev.

Habitat: The entire type series was collected from the old-planted rocky woodland, dominated by the Aleppo pine, *Pinus halepensis* Mill. The spiders were found sitting on the lower surface of the rocks. Most of the additional specimens were collected from pitfall traps in the plain and foothill habitats covered with 'batha' shrubland or planted pine woods.

Oecobius albipunctatus O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872

(Figs 4A, 6A)

Oecobius albipunctatus O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872: 222 (♀); Wunderlich 1995: 590, fig. 4 (♀).

Material examined: Israel: *Upper Galilee:* 1♀, 2♀ subad., northern slope of Mt Meron, 33°01'N 35°24'E, 900 m, 25.iv.2013, S. Zonstein (SMNHTAU).

Distribution: Syria (environs of Damascus) and Israel (Upper Galilee; this is the first record in Israel).

Habitat: The spiders were collected from roadside rocky escarps.

Notes: The pale overall coloration of the preserved specimens (which is light to medium brown in live spiders) looks to be distinguishable from a darker coloration of the syntypes, mentioned in both the original description and Wunderlich (1995). Nevertheless, the collected adult female shares with the syntypes the specific shape of the copulatory structures that is dissimilar to other types of the epigyne, known within the congeners (see Fig. 6A cf. Wunderlich 1995, fig. 4).

Oecobius cambridgei Wunderlich, 1995

(Figs 4B, 5A)

Oecobius cambridgei Wunderlich, 1995: 592, figs 13–16 (♂).

Material examined: Israel: *Upper Galilee:* 1♂, foothills 0.5 km SE 'En Ya'aqov, 33°00.6'N 35°14.3'E, 450 m, 18–23.iii.2006, I. Shtirberg (SMNHTAU); 2♂, northern slope of Mt Meron, environs of Meron Field School, 33°00'N 35°24'E, 800 m, 9–16.v.2007, T. Levanony (SMNHTAU); 1♂, same but 20–29.iv.2008, T. Levanony (SMNHTAU).

Distribution: The species has been previously known only from the type locality: Ain Aata 100 km south-east of Beirut, Lebanon. This is its first record in Israel (Upper Galilee, areas adjoining the border with Lebanon).

Habitat: The spiders were collected from pitfall traps in the dense Mediterranean maquis ('En Ya'aqov) or in the montane oak forest dominated by *Quercus calliprinos* Webb. (Mt Meron).

Notes: The structure of the palp in the collected males entirely corresponds to that depicted by Wunderlich (1995) for the holotype of *O. cambridgei* (Fig. 5A cf. Wunderlich 1995, fig. 15). The conspecific adult female remains unknown.

Oecobius cellariorum (Dugès, 1836)

(Figs 4C, 5B, 6B)

Clotho cellariorum Dugès, 1836: 161.

Oecobius domesticus Lucas, 1846: 101, pl. 2, fig. 1 (♂♀).

Oecobius cellariorum: Simon 1875: 7; Wunderlich 1995: 593, figs 17–20 (♂♀).

Material examined: Israel: *Lower Galilee:* 2♂, 2♀, Alon Tavor Field School, 32°42.4'N 35°24.2'E, 150 m, 5.v.2024, S. Zonstein (SMNHHTAU). *Arava Valley:* 1♀, Qetura, 29°58.2'N 35°03.6'E, 120 m, 17.i.2017, S. Zonstein (SMNHHTAU).

Distribution: Mediterranean, Russia (European part), Azerbaijan, Jordan and Iran. Introduced to the USA, China and Japan (WSC 2024). This is the first record of the species in Israel. Its occurrence from the Galilee in the north to the southern part of the Arava Valley suggests its wide distribution throughout the country.

Habitat: In Israel, the species is found (at least currently) to be synanthropic. The spiders has been collected on the walls inside houses and outbuildings.

Oecobius maculatus Simon, 1870

(Figs 4D, 5C)

Oecobius maculatus Simon, 1870: 346; Wunderlich 1995: 594, figs 12, 29–30 (♂♀).

Material examined: Israel: *Golan Heights:* 1♂, Panyas, 33°14.9'N 35°41.7'E, 350 m, 20.v.2009, S. Zonstein (SMNHHTAU).

Distribution: Mediterranean to Azerbaijan. Introduced to the USA and Mexico (WSC 2024). This is the first record of the species in Israel.

Habitat: The spider was found between stones and leaf litter in riverside woodland.

Oecobius navus Blackwall, 1859

(Figs 4E, 5D, 6C)

Oecobius navus Blackwall, 1859: 266.

Hersiliola brachyplura Strand, 1913: 148 (♂); Strand 1914: 182 (♀), **n. syn.**

Hersiliola brachyplura demaculata Strand, 1914: 183 (♀), **n. syn.**

Oecobius annulipes: Baum 1972: 119 (♀); misidentified, not *O. annulipes* Lucas, 1846 (Wunderlich 1995: 595).

Oecobius brachyplura: Fet 2008: 67.

Oecobius brachyplura demaculatus: Fet 2008: 67.

Oecobius navus: Wunderlich 1995: 595, figs 31–35 (♂♀); Zonstein & Marusik 2013: 62.

Material examined: Israel: *Central Coastal Plain:* 1♂, 0.5 km N Ga'ash (12.5 km NNE Tel Aviv), 32°14'N 34°49'E, 25 m, 15.iv.2015, S. Zonstein (SMNHHTAU); 1♀, campus of Tel Aviv University, 32°06.9'N 34°48.5'E, 45 m, 25.i.2010, S. Zonstein (SMNHHTAU); 2♂, 1♀, same but 30.iv.2013, S. Zonstein (SMNHHTAU); 1♀, same but 26.xii.2021, S. Zonstein (SMNHHTAU); 2♀, same but 22.iii.2023, S. Zonstein (SMNHHTAU); 4♀, Tel Aviv, 32°04'N 34°47'E, 20 m, 8.v.2012, S. Zonstein (SMNHHTAU); 1♂, same but 20.ix.2013, S. Zonstein (SMNHHTAU); 2♀, same, but 29.iii.2019, S.

Fig. 4. *Oecobius* spp., habitus of females (A, C, E, F) and males (B, D, G–I), dorsal: (A) *O. albipunctatus*, (B) *O. cambridgei*, (C) *O. cellariorum*, (D) *O. maculatus*, (E) *O. navus*, (F, G) *O. putus*, (H) *O. teliger*, (I) *O. trimaculatus*. Scale bars: A–H = 0.5 mm, I = 1 mm.

Zonstein (SMNHTAU); 1♂, Bat Yam, 14.vii.2012, A. Weinstein (SMNHTAU). *Southern Coastal Plain*: 3♀, Rehovot, 22.03.2023, S. Zonstein (SMNHTAU).

Distribution: Mediterranean, Russia (European part), Azerbaijan, Jordan and Iran. Introduced to the USA, China and Japan (WSC 2024). In Israel, the species has previously been recorded from Yafo [=Jaffa] (Baum 1972; under *O. annulipes*) and environs of Tel Aviv (Strand 1913, 1914; under *Hersiliola brachyplura* and *H. b. demaculata*, respectively).

Habitat: In Israel, the species has been found only in the anthropogenic environments.

Note: For justification of the proposed new synonymy see Discussion below.

Oecobius putus O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876

(Figs 4F, G, 5E, 6D)

Oecobius putus O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876: 544, pl. 58, fig. 1 (♂♀); Wunderlich 1995: 596, figs 45–48 (♂♀).

Material examined: Israel: *Arava Valley*: 1♂, sand dunes 2 km ESE Samar, 29°49.5'N 35°02.4'E, 70 m, Malaise trap, 1–30.vi.2006, N. Ketner (SMNHTAU); 4♀, Qetura, 29°58.2'N 35°03.6'E, 120 m, 8.xii.2016, S. Zonstein (SMNHTAU); 3♀, Elifaz, 29°47.8'N 35°00.8'E, 120 m, 13.ii.2022, S. Zonstein (SMNHTAU).

Fig. 5. *Oecobius* spp., terminal part of male palp, prolateral (A, D–F, H), retrolateral (B, G, I) and ventral (C): (A) *O. cambridgei*, (B) *O. cellariorum*, (C) *O. maculatus*, (D) *O. navus*, (E) *O. putus*, (F, G) *O. teliger*, (H, I) *O. trimaculatus*. Scale bars: A, C–I = 0.1 mm, B = 0.2 mm. Abbreviations: St – subterminal apophysis, otherwise as in Fig. 2.

Distribution: South-East Mediterranean, Sub-Saharan Africa, Iran, Azerbaijan, Afghanistan and India. Introduced to the USA and Mexico (WSC 2024). This is the first record of the species in Israel.

Habitat: In Israel, the species is found in both natural and anthropogenic environments.

Oecobius teliger O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872

(Figs 4H, 5F, G)

Oecobius teliger O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872: 221, pl. 13, fig. 8 (♂♀); Wunderlich 1995: 598, figs 54–57 (♂♀); Zonstein & Marusik 2013: 62.

Material examined: Israel: *Judean Hills*: 2♂, 0.4 km S Matta', 31°42.6'N 35°03.9'E, 560 m, pitfall traps, 30.vii.2006, I. Shtirberg (SMNHATAU); 4♂, 1♀ subad., Sansan Forest Nature Reserve, 31°21'N 34°53'E, 500 m, pitfall traps, 30.vii.2006, I. Shtirberg (SMNHATAU).

Distribution: The species was described by Pickard-Cambridge (1872) from Beirut and concurrently noted for some localities within the modern Israel (Jerusalem, Tiberias). Later, it was found also in Turkey (Demir *et al.* 2009) and Greece (WSC 2024). All previous Israeli records were dubious, since they were based on non-adult specimens (Wunderlich 1995; Zonstein & Marusik 2013). The present records are thus the first confirmation of the existence of this species in Israel.

Fig. 6. *Oecobius* spp., intact epigyne, ventral: (A) *O. albipunctatus*, (B) *O. cellariorum*, (C) *O. navus*, (D) *O. putus*, (E) *O. trimaculatus*. Scale bars: A, D = 0.05 mm, B, C, E = 0.1 mm.

Habitat: The spiders were collected in the planted forest dominated by the Aleppo pine, *Pinus halepensis* Mill. (Sansan Forest Nature Reserve), as well as in Mediterranean shrubland of 'batha' type on the rocky slopes (Matta').

Oecobius trimaculatus O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872

(Figs 4I, 5H, I, 6E)

Oecobius trimaculatus O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872: 219, pl. 13, fig. 7 (♂♀); Wunderlich 1995: 599, figs 61–65 (♂♀); Zonstein & Marusik 2013: 62; Bosmans & Gavalas 2023: 27, fig. 13A–C (♀).

Material examined: **Israel:** *Judean Hills:* 5♂, 1♀, foothills near Yishpro 3 km W Modi'in, 31°53'N 34°59'E, 200 m, 11–20.iv.2012, I. Bernstein (SMNHHTAU); 1♂, same but 9–17.v.2012, I. Bernstein (SMNHHTAU).

Distribution: The species had been described from the lowlands, also known from ancient times as the Plains of the Jordan, lying north-west of the Dead Sea and bordered in the east by the lower flow of the Jordan River. Later, it was found in Greece (WSC 2024). The present records confirm the existence of this species in Israel, most probably throughout the country.

Habitat: The spiders were collected in pitfall traps, on rocky slopes covered by the Mediterranean shrubland of 'batha' type and grasslands.

DISCUSSION

Unusual structural peculiarities of the sperm duct and the epigyne make *O. armiachi* n. sp. unique within the genus and very different from the type species *O. cellariorum* (Dugès, 1836). Additionally, *O. armiachi* n. sp. lacks an anterior loop of the sperm duct known in most *Oecobius* species, including the genotype; the sperm duct also has several loops located baso-prolaterally, a uniquely shaped rectangular septum and a sclerotized square-shaped epigynal plate. Judging from the great variation of the copulatory organs in the species currently considered in *Oecobius* (in contrast to their similar somatic morphology), it seems that the genus could be split into several genera in future, and the new species described here will be placed in a separate one.

Hersiliola brachyplura and *H. b. demaculata* were transferred to the genus *Oecobius* by Fet (2008). Although we have not examined their types, housed in the Senckenberg Natural History Museum (Frankfurt, Germany), very detailed descriptions by Strand (1913, 1914) are considered quite sufficient for their confident identification.

Strand (1913: 149) noted that in the holotype male of *H. brachyplura*, "Bulbus hat deutlicher vorstehende Fortsätze als es bei *Simoni* der Fall zu sein scheint; wenn man das Glied von der Spitze, parallel zur Unterseite, ansieht, bemerkt man dreikräftige, stumpf zahnförmige Fortsätze, von denen die beiden seitlichen die größten sind und dreieckig erscheinen, während der mittlere mehr warzenförmig zu sein scheint. Vor diesen, also der Spitze näher, kommt eine feine schwarze gekrümmte Leiste

oder Spina zum Vorschein. Im Profil von innen zeigt Bulbus zwei hellgefärbte, etwa kurz zungenförmige, parallel nach unten und vorn gerichtete Fortsätze und vor diesen je einen ganz kleinen schwarzen spitzen Zahn." ("[the] bulb has more clearly protruding processes than appears to be the case with [*Hersiliola*] [*s*] *imoni*; when viewed at the segment from the tip, in parallel to the underside, there are three strong, blunt-tooth-shaped processes, of which the two lateral ones are the largest and appear angular, while the middle one appears to be more wart-shaped. In front of these, i.e. closer to the tip, a fine black curved ridge or spine appears. In profile from the inside, the bulb shows two light-colored, somewhat short tongue-shaped processes directed in parallel downwards and forwards, and in front of each of these a very small black pointed tooth is visible").

Among the characters listed by Strand (1914: 183) in the description of his *Hersiliola brachyplura demaculata*, the structure of the external female copulatory organs was described as follows: "Epigyne erscheint in Flüssigkeit als ein blassgelbliches, fast halbkreisförmiges, hinten abgerundet quergeschnittenes, etwa so langes wie breites Feld, das durch eine etwas dunklere, an beiden Enden aber unscharf begrenzte, subparallelseitige oder mitten leicht verschmälerte Längsbinde, die etwa $\frac{1}{5}$ der Breite des ganzen Feldes einnimmt, geteilt wird; hinten schließt diese Binde eine durch eine braune Linie gebildete ellipsenförmige Längsfigur ein. Trocken gesehen erscheint Epigyne als ein niedriger, abgerundeter Wulst, der besonders an der hinteren Abdachung dicht seidenartig behaart ist und mit einer Medianlängsfurche, welche ein dieselbe fast ausfüllendes, wenig erhöhtes, abgerundetes Längsseptum einschließt, versehen." ("Epigyne appears in liquid as a pale yellowish, almost semicircular, transversely cut field, rounded at the back, about as long as it is wide, which is divided by a slightly darker, but indistinctly defined, subparallel-sided or slightly narrowed longitudinal band, which takes up about $\frac{1}{5}$ of the width of the entire field; at the back this band encloses an elliptical longitudinal figure formed by a brown line. Seen dry, epigyne appears as a low, rounded bulge, which is densely covered with silky hairs, especially on the back slope, and it is provided with a median longitudinal furrow, which encloses a slightly raised, rounded longitudinal septum that almost fills it.").

These details almost definitely indicate that the types of *Hersiliola brachyplura* and *H. b. demaculata* belong to one of the previously described species of the genus *Oecobius*, namely *O. navus* (Figs 5C, 6C), which is the only member of *Oecobius* found in and around Tel Aviv, including both Yafo and Rehovot, the type localities of the two taxa described by Strand (1913, 1914). Thus, these two names—*Hersiliola brachyplura* Strand, 1913 and *Hersiliola brachyplura demaculata* Strand, 1914—are considered herein the junior subjective synonyms of the widespread *O. navus* Blackwall, 1859.

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